

IN UZBEKISTAN CULTIVATION OF COMPETITION OF THE ENVIRONMENT INTO BEING IS COMING AND HIS LEGAL BASIS.

Ismailov Toirjon

Tashkent state university of economics
master of Economics direction

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14436466>

Annotation. Uzbekistan the present day trade, industry and the other one is how many in the area, developing it has been. This environment and it on up, the market to pass required continues. This while important legal framework require it. In this article Uzbekistan in the competitive environment to the legal framework review, we will and analyze.

Key words: competition, legal basis, the law, the monopoly, pure competition, entrepreneurship, healthy competition, work out

Independence in the years of the republic, in a small business of production and a healthy competitive environment of the new year, and form the legal foundation was created. Independence initial years monopoly against the policy of maintaining and healthy competition in the formation of age, independent Uzbekistan, to news be will, although our republic the president Sh.M. Mirziyoev by monopoly against a policy get go as the complexity rational approach to this issue guarantee is a service made has been.

The country's business activities in the development of competition and the role he is one. In this regard, in our state by monopolistic activity limitation and competition in the legal regulation in issues particular attention paid.

2024 year 5 August Uzbekistan Republic President Sh.M. Mirziyoev by competition development of the concept considered is. Then, the energy, airport services and other areas of 17 types of state monopoly finish is expected. Permits and licenses mandatory insurance will be replaced, natural monopoly in the field of independent regulator the issues of the analysis was.

Certain make, last five years, in over 25 more products on the competitive environment improved. Business type on competition restrict exclusive rights cancelled have been. The state with the participation of enterprises of 42 percent reduction, business entities and the number of at 1.6 times have increased.

In the year 2023 "Competition on" the law of new in the wording taken was. Competition development, and consumers rights protect to the committee additional impressive powers was given. Same on a basis out go and study according, some organizations to compete contrary decisions that take it to, directly, the contract conclusion, the trade in superior position to use such as cases there are.

In this regard, industry affairs coverage and effectiveness to increase in order "competition for the development of the concept of work were out of. The economy of the state participation, reduce, market access liberalization, business equal conditions to create on your next steps are determined. Documents of the business market and free access regulatory substances and excess demand cancelled be projected.

Regulated material burden decrease aimed to relaxation of the introduction is, in particular, access, allowing the process of and licenses responsibility and compulsory insurance with will be replaced.

Natural monopoly sectors, independent market regulator of the introduction is. Natural monopoly sectors with mutually bound and competition development of the possibility of the goods in the market of natural monopoly entities participation limit.

That is in addition to, directly done, which is state procurement of the scale were reduced to, state procurement competitive methods fully will be transferred. Competition for limiting individual features to be able to the state of the help, this is including, exclusive rights, privileges, preferences and relaxation cancelled was.

State bodies of information of the system, the mutual integration making through social significance have the products price formation of the chain, all of the unit digital monitoring to the path is put. Competition against the agreement, and behavior action, language combination, the conditions about the information you provide who individuals disclose to failure and reward system, the introduction of is.

From concept to implementation to increase as a result of the energy, oil and gas, water resources, road construction, rail way and airport services such as a number of area 17 of the types of state monopoly step-by-step finish measures is seen

That is in addition to, public procurement to competition contrary to the action on the front to make, this is the process of transparency it provides. Commodity and raw materials exchange offers were increased, to the buyer the choice of the possibility will be expanded.

The President Sh.M. Mirziyoev by the economy in the state share to reduce, some functions step-by-step private sector to transfer the need stressed. It goods, finance and digital in the market competition status of constant analysis you do, the order improvement on the suggestions to add to go to the function put.

In the last three years during in-place competition legislation to the contrary, which is over 2000 more actions identified. In most cases this local as well as the governor and the minister Azerbaijanis these documents is. In this regard, the Competition committee of the regional department of the work revive, personnel skills to increase the necessity of showing was.

Today's day in a competitive environment you create to free competition, and protect to, and monopoly aimed at a number of legal regulatory network act, system, the creation of the most important issue has become. Single economic width of goods, services and financial instruments are free to be moved, free economic activity and competition guarantee in the constitution defined given. Of the constitution, article 53 of "Market relations development aimed at the Uzbekistan economy on the basis of diversity in the form of property, the organization is. State the right column that into account taking, economic activity, entrepreneurship and work for the freedom, all the property of the form equal to that rights and legal aspects of the protection of equal protection that guarantees that consolidation was". In the country monopolistic activity and competitive activity limitation with associated 2 law accepted has been. In particular, 1996

27-December taken made "Goods in the market of monopolistic activity limitation and competition is on and the "Natural monopoly on" the law on the basis of regulated shall be". Free competition, strengthen and monopoly that rule to limit aimed legal

norms of the republic of Uzbekistan in the republic accepted has been the law in its reflection has found. Uzbekistan , republic of the Civil code, 1999-the year 19-August in "Natural monopoly on law, 1996 26-April accepted has been "The rights of protect to on" the law, 1998-25 years-in December, accepted has been "Advertising on" the law of all among them. Goods and services in the market competition and monopolistic activity control of the legal regulatory network that act on the system of Uzbekistan republic of the Civil code of the particular norms also includes. Civil code according, civil rights, the competition limit to use the way it is put.

Above listed are the laws of most main thing "of goods in the market of monopolistic activity limitation and competition on" the law is. Free competitive environment, new build, it save you stay, the necessary toe 'did it again, restore, competition method of resolution is to find and explain like to focus on. " Uzbekistan – 2030" Strategy , according furthermore, the monopoly sector of the market the principles of consistent conduct, in the economy, the private sector share to increase, businesses free business be doing for the most comfortable conditions to create issue will is, to him according,

- In the economy, non-governmental sector , the share of 85 percent to deliver, the state share of the available 2.3 thousand enterprises , the number of 6 times reduce.

- In the republic of 17 types of state monopoly cancel to, this sector to the private sector wide to attract to, the state reserve, only the trunk of the energy and transport sectors, public administration and security with area keep stay.

Iron is either transportation, the car of the road construction and management, gas and electrical supplies to give services to the private sector out to give.

- Irrigation, waste and re - work, public facilities, energy and heat supply system management as the state monopoly in the sphere of private partnership mechanisms broad introduction to.

- Local business entities of strategic useful minerals of the deposits of giving the practice expansion, gold, silver, colored metals, tungsten, and to mine issued permits, the number of 4 times increase.

- Tax system stability ensure to order in business for methodology' the value and profit tax rates for three years during increase guarantee.

- Tax system digitization, simplify, and all entrepreneurs for equal opportunities to create, the official sectors – no legal activity from preferred and advantageous be to all necessary conditions provide.

- Small and central business international market out opportunities for expansion, micro financing, development, innovation and the startup support and large business with the cooperation for the development of a new instrument to practice introduced are.

- The family business on the basis of employment in providing simple "methodology's labor «from - work out to the stage to take, equipment to purchase and get to preferential loan in the amount of 100 million sums to increase, such as issues raised.

Business entities in all services, in a "single window" principle on the basis of an online portal through and services to show the time on average 3 times reduce. Product and raw materials of particular types of limit and the stock in the distribution of major the system, as well as, business out of the increase to permits, licenses, certificates, issuance of, come to, as existing administrative barriers monopolistic tendencies in the more opportunity it creates.

609 units in 2016 state assets investment to add and a new job of the creation of the condition with “zero” in the purchase of value was sold. Today's day in ta 413 state assets, the including 65 of dollars “zero” purchase on the value of the public to the trading methodology’ the year that was. Effectively in a competitive environment you create to the following measures of implementation and enforcement increase requires a will: a) the economy is in state monopolizing each how to show that to the maximum extent eliminated are. Do this to a business, the development and the economy of the state by the management system improvement for relatively favorable conditions to create aimed deep institutional reforms necessary; b) the market in the context of being into coming monopoly in the market dominate abuse make to avoid to get. State institutions of the competition development provide should. Without effective innovation, lower costs and prices, and products of high quality to achieve, in other words, the whole of the economy competitiveness increase can not. Uzbek in the state's competitive luxury environment for the formation aimed at in the policy of privatization, state property at the expense of the ownership of other forms of form to come in the main keeps. Privatization as a result of, first of all, the property owners into the hands of delivered, secondly, the economy and subsequently the competition environment into the body of brings. So Uzbek competition subsequently the environment into the body of both come key is either, competition deny which state monopoly non -, various economic forms of existence based on and possible , as free competition requires which the market system is passed.. So Uzbekistan republic of the Oliy Majlis by 27 1996-December “Goods in the market of monopolistic activity limitation and competition about the «on the new law to adopt did not. This is the law of monopolistic activity and ever competition and avoid to get, it limit, stops organizational and legal basis of the outline giving, republic of the goods in the market competitive relations formation and effective follow that ensuring it is focused on. Also, the law in mainly two important either, i.e. first of all, monopoly against to comb for tar fundamental new view is, it is available and preserved remaining monopolist by market dominant position abuse of the prevention get and it eradicate to will keep, secondly, the most basic, important issues to be considered, which is the small business of production and a healthy competitive environment of the formation that is defined has been. The law monopoly applies that a ban, but in the market with their dominance effects came out negative occurrence to prevent to take directed. In law implied bans also developed market economy countries Uzbekistan and other transition period as the economy of countries for typical , which is the monopolist behavior against a set. The following act monopoly against legislation to the contrary is: - receives the ambassador compliance entities by the market in the prevailing environment, the state of abusing be (5- article); - economic entities competition to limit directed transactions (mutually agreed of) (article 6); - state administration bodies and local government bodies competition to limit the focused actions (article 7); - dishonest competition (article 8). Monopoly against active measures implementation increase to 0 in 1992 in Uzbek monopoly against the body as the Finance ministry of Monopoly against and price policy of the chief department of the organization has been. The department listed in included in the monopoly position in the enterprises, the product of price and profitability regulated, and stand to the right were given. In 1996, this department on the basis of the Finance ministry under the small business, production and competition development methodology of the pest establishment was. In the year 2000, the republic, the president of Uzbekistan , republic of the small business of production and competition for the

development of the state committee of the organization for the resolution on the decree according monopoly against the body, the finance ministry from the structure was removed and the independent state committee was transformed. Later, this methodology of the pest activity further improvement and effectiveness to increase in order Uzbekistan Republic President Decree, according to this organization in the small business production, competition and entrepreneurship support of the state committee was transformed. In the republic of competition, cultivation of the environment form come out being all the work of the market economy structure to conduct to find the serve will. O'zbek Uzbekistan republic of get which go monopoly against the policy of an important either of one - this monopolist enterprises of goods in the market, the position of the standing column of the position of the abuse of prevention get and him the way is put on the control of the taking go from to. Exactly the same in order for the monopolist enterprises State register of the office being, to him a particular network in the column position to be able toe 'present in the directory is included in. O'zbek Uzbekistan Republic "Competition on" the law of article 6 in a "superior position" concept as follows explained: "Superior position in the commodity or financial market receives the ambassador the compliance of the entity or entities of the group be economic compliance entities associated with the case to him in his business out increase and the competition of the position solution, the effects show, the relevant market and other economic compliance entities accessing difficult to use or their economic activity freedom in a different way to limit the possibility that gives the speed of the cases. Goods in the market , which is agriculture compliance entities or individuals, group of goods , the share: 1) fifty and more than percent up on Esty; 2) thirty - five percent , fifty percent, up in size to be, it has the following conditions: agriculture compliance entities of goods in the market share at least a year for stable is stand; goods in the market and other economic compliance entities (national competition) in the appropriate stakes relative to the amount that is stand; this market new economic compliance of entities (competition readers) to enter the chance to be the terms specified if it is, the same farm, the compliance of the entity or entities of the group and of the position column is the position as a recognized is". To register taken ambassador receives compliance of businesses with their products, the price (tariff)of the world or profitability at the level of Finance at the ministry of or in the place of financial structure from the declaration is to be held must. In the republic for the development listed to access the directory (network)of the world market in the position of regulating in the state of a number of methods uses. This method from two separate should be: 1. Monopoly in a position companies for their product prices of most high - level or profitability of the limits of the outline put. 2. O'z monopoly position of abuse made monopolistic associations toe 'become remove. This method Uzbekistan republic of (6 2001-December 310-II dated) law with approved "Responsibility limited and methodology responsible society on" on the basis of out carried. O'zbek Uzbekistan Republic "of the consumer rights protect to the in (1996, 26 April) of the law based on to compete, same including the republic to the market with specified requirements to answer that does not of goods to the production the way that does not put a mechanism to create too special attention is given. Natural monopoly state either with regulated held in that they are the product (service)s prices and tariffs of the level, as well as, offered which are goods and services to the type of the related main indicators and provisions signs their into gets. Next year, the State of the register, keeping the methodology and the improvement of the members go to, small business and private entrepreneurship

development, foreign exchanges of investment into coming as a result of the built which are enterprises, the weight its nest in an increase and the other factors in the effects of many monopolist enterprises of goods in the market share of the reduction to the relationship with the State from the register is produced. In the network monopoly is a how much of the association end, in independent businesses into the body of brought, that while the competitive environment, the further strengthening to take come. The present day in the country work output of goods world market competitiveness to ensure also critical task is. This reason is also "in the country, and created technologies of competitiveness, providing, "know-how" samples to create, modern information and communication technologies introduction to, that the high quality of product work to provide toe 'citizens of systematic measures of implementation of the increase" should.

Every one in the country - specific situation, that is, the economy level of its scale and This law application, check out the circle of the displacement, i.e. its norms of Uzbekistan republic of the Goods in the market competition, the effects of the individuals between relationships in a wide spread. These individuals, mainly, local and foreign legal entities, in the execution of executive power bodies, local self - self - management bodies, physical entities and entrepreneurs. Monopolistic activity limitation and competition development on the law of the independent right to have that objects with associated in the relationship are not applied. Competition and monopoly regulating governing the antimonopoly of law number of the president decrees, the ministers of the cabinet decisions, Uzbekistan to the republic of monopoly against the authorities of the order and of instructs also an important role plays. In Uzbekistan monopoly against to fight the monopoly of activities to limit and competition policy formation, it is out to increase of trying the beginning is, this area of foreign exchanges of experience and the republic of the economy of the transition period, the status and the existing legal system itself that is specific into account taking without work out. Reforms step-by-step done increase, market infrastructure formation and development, in its turn, monopoly against the policy improvement and competition for the development of the necessary opportunity they brought

In the economy, work in and out of, market relationships, competition in the field of relations regulating look at, Uzbekistan , republic of the legislative chamber by 2023-14-year-in February received was, and 2023-2 year-in march, the senate by approved Competition about the law of working out.

This law is the basis for the purpose of competition in the field of relations regulating in, commodity or financial market competition to limit, also competition or natural monopolies in the conditions of consumers rights and legitimate interests in derogation care take come in or out come can that the actions control to be done to increase and to them an end put if, his main principles: Dark competition – monopoly against the law out increase, the monopoly to prevent to take and all enterprises for equal conditions own into gets. Thus, all participants have their own advantage according, unfair advantage and disadvantage without to compete for equal chance has. This innovation, efficiency and consumer choice to help will.

CONCLUSION

Conclusion in that note to take it is noteworthy, in Uzbekistan competitive environment for the emergence to be, economic development for an important factor is. The state of competition methodology of the pest organized, be and the business environment to improve focus honest competition, development of and competition against the movement prevent to

get on the way is an important step. The government by done being various reforms and initiatives mainly of consumers rights and legitimate interests priority to ensure, goods and services the quality of and improve and ultimately consumers and enterprises benefits bring and this is like the field is directed. Also, competitive luxury market in the dark the competition, legitimacy, transparency like principles the incarnation makes. This consumers with quality products, provide to, at affordable prices through purchases to make, conscious decisions to take to, their rights and obligations you understand and false or distracting from the practice escape like improve opportunities will. In short, I say, without competition, the economic development of the recently does not give. Market economy development , the most important factor in competition.

References:

- 1.Dani Rodrik. "Globalization Paradox", 2011. 516 p
- 2.Paul Krugman, "Trade and the National Economy" - 1986
- 3.James Marcuse, "Trade and The Gains from Trade with Imperfect Competition" - 1989
- 4.Belyakov, S. (2023). THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DIGITIZATION OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES. Science technology Digital Finance, 1(4), 10-20. <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf/article/view/bso>
- 5.Sardar B., Ibrahimovic T. K. Digital Transformation Directions in the Restaurant Business //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY. – 2023. – T. 2. – No. 2. – C. 1-4.